

**THE CONCEPT OF FOLKLORISM AND ITS POSITION
IN LITERARY STUDIES****Baxitova Umida Rustem qizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18454298>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29st January 2026Accepted: 30th January 2026Online: 31th January 2026**KEYWORDS***folklorism, literature, folklore, typology, artistic language, literary process***ABSTRACT**

The article explores the phenomenon of folklorism and its role in literature. Theoretical approaches to studying folklorism are analyzed based on the works of U.B.Dalgat, A.I.Lazarev, and contemporary researchers such as T.M.Stepanova and L.P.Bessonova. Special attention is given to the typology of folklorism, its manifestations in literary works, and its influence on the artistic language. The study demonstrates how folkloric elements contribute to the preservation of national traditions and enrich literary creativity.

The term “folklorism” was introduced as a scientific term in French folklore studies in the 19th century. It is used to denote the interest of writers, literary scholars, and cultural figures in oral folk art, as well as their incorporation of plots, motifs, and images characteristic of folk oral poetry. The issue of folklorism is closely intertwined with the relationship between literature and folklore, and it is typically examined from several angles. On one hand, the influence of oral poetic traditions on the works of individual writers is studied, while on the other hand, the existence and fate of literary works within the folklore environment are analyzed. Additionally, it is of great significance that the legacy of many writers who were active in the 19th and early 20th centuries cannot be fully comprehended without considering their work as collectors and researchers of folk folklore.

Folklore has served as an inexhaustible source for writers in understanding the spiritual life of the people, and has also been one of the important tools for enriching their artistic creativity with elements of folk culture. In this process, the use of plots, motifs, images, and genre-stylistic forms characteristic of oral folk creativity is observed. In Russian literature, folklorism is closely connected with the ideas of populism and historicism. These concepts took shape in the late 18th - first quarter of the 19th century both in the West and in Russia as a result of the desire to comprehend national cultural identity, to reveal the peculiarities of national character, literature, art, and the distinctive features of the people’s language.

In this regard, not only the artistic practice of writers but also their theoretical views on the interrelationships between literature and folklore, as well as their perspectives on the role of oral folk creations in shaping literary language, are of great importance in understanding folklorism. One of the main tasks in studying folklorism is to analyze the direct and reciprocal influence of oral poetic traditions not only on individual literary works but also on the entire

creative output of a writer. This, in turn, serves to broaden the possibilities of creatively utilizing folklore plots, motifs, and images in various genres and forms of literature.

In literary studies, the concept of folklorism is interpreted as the process of integrating elements of folk creativity and traditional cultural codes into written literary texts, that is, transforming them and presenting them in written works. Through folklorism, the writer incorporates ethnographic and ethnological information, mythological and epic plots, as well as characters with figurative and typological characteristics into their work. The main task in this process is narrativization, that is, the reformation of oral and visual folklore elements in the literary context and their integration into the written literary process.

Terminologically, folklorism has been defined differently by a number of scientific schools and researchers:

In Russian literary studies, V.Ya.Propp [1] views folklorism as “the reconstruction of plots, motifs, and archetypes taken by a writer from folk oral tradition in a literary text”. (Propp, 1989).

In scholarly literature, it is noted that folklorism manifests itself in various forms of interaction between literature and folk oral creativity. In the research of T.M.Stepanova and L.P.Bessonova [2], the necessity of systematizing folklorisms is especially emphasized, as the authors, expressing the view that authors use folkloric material for various purposes and methods, propose to classify them as follows:

1. Creative (independent) folklorism.

In this type, the author consciously reworks, renews, and adapts folklore materials to a modern artistic system. Folklore images, motifs, or genre forms acquire new meanings and perform independent artistic functions in the work. Here, folklore participates not as a source, but as a tool for creative thinking.

2. Adapted folklorism is achieved by simplifying folklore texts and images, making them understandable for modern readers or viewers. Certain archaic, violent, or elements that do not conform to contemporary aesthetic norms are removed. This type is widely used, especially in children's literature and mass culture.

3. The main goal of ethnographic folklorism is to preserve and restore folklore samples in their original state as much as possible. In this, the author or performer strives not to alter the folklore, but to preserve its historical, genre, and poetic characteristics. This type is directly related to folklore festivals, stage performances, and ethnographic research.

According to U.B.Dalgat: “Folklore is oral folk art that reflects the collective experience, traditions, and worldview of the people”. [3.12]

Literature, on the contrary, is an integral and written form of art that reflects the individual creativity of the author. At the same time, the boundaries between folklore and literature are not rigid; they interact within the framework of creative processes.

Lazarev[4] considers folklorism not merely as a form of plot or motifs borrowed from folklore, but as a creative phenomenon enriched with unique artistic qualities, recreated with social and cultural mastery through the aesthetic and poetic functions of folklore in a literary work.

In his opinion, folklorism is the characteristic-terminal note of the interaction between literature and folklore. Although the term's meaning is interpreted differently by various

scholars due to the lack of a definitive definition, Lazarev interprets it from the perspective of aesthetic, stylistic, and social interplay.

The concept of folklorism differs from the "connection of genres, plots, and symbols between folklore and literature" proposed by scholars such as U.B. Dalgat. In Lazarev's view, folklorism is seen as a process of genuine creative transformation and reflection.

In Uzbek literary studies, the relationship between folklore and written literature began to be systematically studied from the second half of the 20th century. Notably, Z.Masharipova's [5] textbook "Written Literature and Folk Oral Creativity" extensively covers the role of folklore as a source in the development of classical and modern Uzbek literature. The author scientifically analyzes the thematic and ideological motifs, plot and character systems of folklore works in Uzbek classical literature, as well as their significance in shaping artistic methods and linguistic richness (Masharipova, 2008). This research serves to understand folklorism as a natural and integral part of the literary process.

One of the fundamental works that specifically studied the problem of folklorism is G.Muminov's doctoral dissertation "Folklorism in Modern Uzbek Literature" [6]. The author establishes the theoretical foundations of folklorism in Uzbek literature and reveals its typological features. The dissertation comprehensively analyzes the poetic functions of folklore motifs, their influence on the creator's individual style, and their role in the development of genres (Muminov, 1994). This work serves as an important scientific reference for evaluating folklorism as an independent literary category.

Additionally, research on the influence of folk oral traditions in Alisher Navoiy's work is of great importance in illuminating the issue of folklorism. The artistic reinterpretation of folk images, symbols, and plot models in Navoiy's works demonstrates the elevation of folklore traditions to a high aesthetic level in classical literature.

F.Jalalov's [7] research dedicated to Hamza's work highlights the integration of folklore motifs with socio-educational ideas in modern literature.

Overall, these scientific studies provide a basis for evaluating folklorism as a continuous process in the historical development of literature. Furthermore, it demonstrates the necessity of a systematic analysis of the artistic and functional features of folklore in the poetics of classical literature..

References:

1. Пропп В.Я. Фольклор и действительность. — М.: Наука, 1976. — 325 с.
2. Степанова Т. М., Бессонова Л. П. Типология фольклоризма литературных текстов // Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. Серия 2: Филология и искусствоведение. — 2007. — № 2. — С. 245–249.
3. Далгат У.Б. Литература и фольклор: теоретические аспекты. — Москва: Наука, 1981. — 303 с.
4. Лазарев А. И. Проблема изучения фольклоризма русской литературы 1870–1890-х гг. / А.И. Лазарев. — Сборник «Русская литература 1870–1890 гг.: Проблемы литературного процесса», 1985. — С. 45–102.
5. Машарипова З. Ёзма адабиёт ва халқ оғзаки ижоди : ўқув қўлланма. – Тошкент : Иқтисод-молия, 2008. – 125 б.

6. Муминов Г. Фольклоризм в современной узбекской литературе: автореф. дис. ... д-ра филол. наук. – Тошкент, 1994.

7. Жалолов Ф. Хамза поэзияси ва халқ оғзаки ижоди. – Тошкент: Фан, 1975. – 56 б

